

Motor Impairments in Autism Spectrum Disorder: Implications for Intervention and Research

Bryan V. Catama^{1*}

¹School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts, Saint Louis University, Baguio City, Philippines

Abstract: Motor impairments, such as unusual posture, are a critical aspect of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) that affects individuals of all ages and influences how the disorder manifests. This review examines the prevalence and consequences of motor impairments in ASD, exploring their relationship with key characteristics, potential neurobiological factors, and implications for intervention and future research. By reviewing recent studies, literature reviews, and theoretical perspectives, this review reveals the complex interplay between motor abilities, sensory processing, social cognition, and overall development in individuals with ASD. The findings show that motor impairments are not just co-occurring features but are integral to the condition, affecting the severity of social communication difficulties, restricted and repetitive behaviors, and adaptive functioning. This review highlights the need for a shift in ASD research and intervention, moving away from isolated approaches and embracing a more comprehensive perspective that considers the significant impact of motor impairments on individuals with ASD.

Keywords: Fine Motor Skills; Gross Motor Skills; Motor Interventions; Autism Spectrum Disorder; Neurodevelopmental Disorders; Developmental Coordination Disorder

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 25 July, 2024; **Published:** 30 July, 2024

How to cite this article: Bryan V. Catama (2024). *Motor Impairments in Autism Spectrum Disorder: Implications for Intervention and Research*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(7), 97-108. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13239488>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition that affects social communication, behavior, and sensory processing from an early age [1, 2]. It is characterized by persistent difficulties in social interaction, restricted interests, and unusual sensory reactions. The disorder's lifelong nature is rooted in its neurobiological basis [3-7]. The diverse range of abilities and challenges within the ASD population highlights the need for personalized understanding and support [8]. Approximately 1% of the global population has ASD, with higher rates in high-income countries, which raises questions about the impact of awareness and diagnostic practices on these rates [1]. Individuals with ASD often have co-occurring psychiatric conditions, such as anxiety disorders, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), and mood disorders. These conditions worsen their well-being and require comprehensive, integrated care [9]. The connection between ASD and other conditions highlights the complex interaction of genetic, environmental, and neurobiological factors that shape the experiences of individuals with ASD [10-13]. Recent research emphasizes the significance of motor impairments and atypical postural control in individuals with ASD, beyond the traditional diagnostic criteria of social communication and repetitive behaviors [14-17]. These motor challenges have a profound impact on development, coordination, and overall quality of life. For instance, difficulties with motor planning and

coordination can limit the acquisition of new skills, such as writing or participating in sports, which in turn affect social interaction and learning opportunities [3, 18, 19]. A comprehensive understanding of ASD requires a holistic approach that considers not only the core social and behavioral characteristics but also the significant role of motor impairments in shaping individual experiences. This literature review provides a comprehensive examination of motor impairments in ASD, with a focus on atypical postural control. By synthesizing current research, this review aims to clarify the connections between motor abilities, sensory processing, social cognition, and overall development in individuals with ASD across the lifespan. The review will explore the prevalence and nature of motor deficits in ASD, their relationship to core ASD symptoms, and their impact on daily activities and quality of life. It will also investigate the neurobiological basis of these impairments, including cerebellar structure and function, and evaluate current intervention strategies. This review aims to highlight the fundamental role of motor challenges in ASD manifestation and advocate for a shift in ASD research and intervention. Ultimately, it seeks to inform future research directions, clinical practice, and the development of more effective, personalized interventions that address both motor and core ASD challenges in an integrated manner.

2. Motor Impairments in Autism Spectrum Disorder

2.1 Overview of motor deficits in ASD

Motor impairments are a common and persistent problem for individuals with ASD, extending beyond the social and communication difficulties that define the condition [20]. These deficits affect both fine motor skills, such as precise hand movements for writing, and gross motor skills, which involve coordination and balance during activities like sports or walking [21, 22]. Posture control challenges, observed in unusual walking patterns and balance difficulties, highlight the sensory and motor difficulties associated with ASD [23, 24]. Notably, these motor impairments often emerge early in childhood, potentially even before social and communication difficulties. This underscores the importance of early screening and intervention [23]. As these motor challenges persist throughout life, they can significantly impact an individual's ability to interact with their environment, learn new skills, and fully participate in social and academic activities [25, 26].

2.2 Relationship between motor skills and autism severity

Research indicates a strong link between motor skills and the severity of ASD, suggesting that motor impairments are integral to the condition rather than just a coincidence [20]. Studies have found significant correlations between deficits in gross motor skills (e.g., coordination and balance) and fine motor skills (e.g., precise hand movements) and the severity of ASD's core symptoms, including social communication and repetitive behavior impairments [27, 28]. Notably, early motor skills development may even predict later challenges with ASD symptoms, as delays in these skills may indicate greater difficulties in childhood [29]. This potential for motor skills to predict or influence ASD severity underscores the importance of early, comprehensive motor assessments, which should be integrated into diagnostic and intervention approaches [30]. Addressing these motor challenges may be crucial to unlocking the full potential of individuals with ASD across various developmental areas.

2.3 Association of motor impairments with social deficits

The link between motor impairments and social deficits in ASD is a crucial area of research, with implications for understanding and treating the condition. Studies consistently show that children with ASD often have motor impairments, affecting both fine motor skills (e.g., hand movements) and gross motor skills (e.g., balance and coordination) [31, 32, 21]. They may also struggle with more complex abilities, such as praxis (planning and executing movements) and interpersonal synchrony (coordinating movements with others). These motor deficits are not simply a coincidence, but are connected to social communication difficulties. Research has found that weaker motor skills are correlated with greater social deficits [21]. The underlying neurobiological basis of this association is becoming clearer, with evidence suggesting disrupted functional connectivity between brain regions critical for visual-motor integration and social cognition, such as the medial prefrontal cortex and amygdala [33, 34]. Furthermore, research has identified

unique deficits in embodied simulation in ASD, which involves integrating visual input with motor output [35]. These deficits may contribute to difficulties in imitation and acquiring social skills. These findings emphasize the importance of considering motor impairments not only as a common co-occurring feature of ASD but also as a potential core aspect of the disorder that influences the development and presentation of social deficits. Therefore, ASD treatment approaches should include comprehensive motor assessments and targeted interventions that address both motor and social domains [36, 37].

2.4 Impact of sensorimotor problems on daily living activities

Individuals with ASD face significant sensorimotor challenges that impact daily activities and essential functional skills for independence and quality of life. These challenges lead to difficulties with fine and gross motor skills, postural control, and manual dexterity, affecting tasks like dressing, eating, and toileting [38, 39]. The underlying neurological basis for these difficulties involves altered cortical-striatal processes and reduced functional connectivity in the sensorimotor network, resulting in deficits in motor planning and execution [40, 26]. Notably, individuals with ASD exhibit larger postural sway and increased attention demands during motor tasks, suggesting that even simple activities require greater cognitive resources [41]. These sensorimotor challenges persist from childhood to adulthood, with evidence of impaired motor skills and atypical functional connectivity in middle-aged adults with ASD [26]. The widespread nature of these issues underscores the need for targeted interventions that address sensorimotor deficits throughout life, potentially improving overall functioning and reducing ASD symptom severity [42, 40]. Individuals with ASD face significant sensorimotor challenges that impact essential daily activities and skills necessary for independence and quality of life, such as dressing, eating, and toileting [38, 39]. These difficulties arise from altered cortical-striatal processes and reduced functional connectivity in the sensorimotor network, leading to deficits in motor planning and execution [40, 26]. Individuals with ASD exhibit larger postural sway and increased cognitive demands during motor tasks, indicating that even simple activities require more cognitive resources [41]. These challenges persist from childhood to adulthood, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to improve overall functioning and reduce ASD symptom severity [42, 40].

3. Postural Control in Autism Spectrum Disorder

3.1 Understanding postural control issues in individuals with ASD

Postural control issues in individuals with ASD involve complex sensorimotor deficits that affect balance and stability. A key challenge is the impaired integration of multiple sensory inputs, particularly in visual and somatosensory processing [43, 44]. This leads to increased postural sway and reduced complexity in side-to-side movements. Moreover, individuals with ASD require more cognitive resources for tasks involving postural control, even simple balance activities [41]. Notably, social stimuli also impact postural control, with increased sway during tasks involving faces compared to objects, especially in individuals with more severe ASD [45]. These postural control issues persist from early development through adulthood, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions throughout life [46, 47]. Furthermore, the specific patterns of postural sway observed in ASD, such as greater sway area and deficits in side-to-side control, not only distinguish it from other neurodevelopmental disorders but also have potential as sensitive diagnostic markers [48, 49].

3.2 Link between postural control and motor skills

The connection between postural control and motor skills is complex and can be seen at different stages of development and in various neurological conditions, especially in ASD. Studies show that sensorimotor processing and multisensory integration are essential for maintaining postural stability, which is the basis for developing fundamental motor skills [47, 50]. People with ASD often have increased postural sway and struggle with processing sensory information, leading to difficulties with both fine and gross motor control [51, 52]. These postural control deficits affect not only basic balance and locomotor skills but also have broader impacts on more complex motor behaviors and overall functional development [53]. Notably, there is a two-way relationship between postural stability and motor skill proficiency,

where improvements in one area can enhance performance in the other. This interconnectedness highlights the importance of targeting both postural control and motor skills in assessment and intervention strategies, particularly for individuals with neurodevelopmental disorders [54, 55].

3.3 Mediating effects of sequential memory on self-care performance

The connection between sequential memory and self-care performance in individuals with ASD is influenced by various factors, including visual-motor integration, cognitive processes, and functional outcomes. Research by Lin et al. [56] shows that sequential memory plays a key role in linking visual-motor integration to self-care performance in young children with ASD, highlighting its significance in daily functioning. These findings align with broader research on memory processes in ASD, which suggests difficulties in short-term memory and episodic long-term memory, particularly in the visual domain [57]. Executive functioning also affects the relationship between sequential memory and self-care performance. A study by Landsiedel and Williams [58] found that executive set-shifting and inhibitory control abilities significantly impact prospective memory in adults with ASD. Furthermore, selective attention in context memory [59] and the subject-performed task effect in working memory [60] suggest that multiple cognitive factors contribute to memory performance in individuals with ASD, potentially affecting their self-care abilities. These insights stress the importance of tailored interventions that target both visual-motor integration and sequential memory to improve self-care outcomes in individuals with ASD.

4. Interventions and Management Strategies

4.1 Role of exercise in improving health outcomes in individuals with ASD

Exercise offers benefits beyond physical fitness, showing promise as a therapeutic tool for improving health outcomes in individuals with ASD [61]. Customized exercise interventions, such as aerobic exercise and game-based programs, have been found to significantly improve cognitive function, including attention and memory. Additionally, these interventions have been shown to reduce stereotyped motor behaviors commonly seen in individuals with ASD [62, 63]. Moreover, exercise has been shown to have a positive impact on social skills and behavioral challenges, potentially promoting greater social interaction while reducing emotional reactivity and sleep disturbances [64]. The benefits of exercise may be attributed to its ability to reduce neuroinflammation, enhance brain plasticity, and release mood-boosting endorphins [65, 66]. Given this growing body of evidence, it is clear that exercise should be a crucial component of comprehensive treatment strategies for individuals with ASD. This involves incorporating structured exercise interventions as well as increasing physical activity in daily routines.

4.2 Evaluation of motor interventions on gross motor skills development

The effectiveness of motor interventions on gross motor skill development in individuals with ASD is evaluated using a comprehensive approach that includes standardized assessments, functional measures, and task-specific observations [67, 68]. Standardized tools, such as the TGMD-2 and BOT-2, provide objective measures of improvements in locomotion, object control, balance, and coordination. These tools accurately measure the impact of interventions on core gross motor abilities [69, 70]. In addition to standardized assessments, evaluating functional performance, such as self-care skills and daily activities, provides valuable insights into the real-world implications of improved motor skills [71]. Task-specific games or activities incorporated into the evaluation process further enhance understanding of how interventions influence movement accuracy, form, and the child's ability to perform specific motor tasks with reduced prompting [68]. This multi-dimensional evaluation approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of motor interventions in promoting meaningful improvements in gross motor development and functional outcomes for individuals with ASD.

4.3 Effects of a motor activity program on social skills in students with ASD

Emerging evidence suggests that motor activity programs, typically focused on improving motor skills, can have a significant positive impact on social skills in students with ASD [72]. These programs provide valuable opportunities for students with ASD to engage in social interaction within a structured and supportive environment. They include

activities ranging from inclusive physical education to structured interventions that incorporate social games [73]. Participating in physical activities, such as team-based games or cooperative tasks, naturally promotes communication, collaboration, and social cognition development [72]. Additionally, these programs may improve motor abilities, such as coordination and balance, allowing for greater participation in group activities and reducing social anxiety, which further enhances social engagement [74]. The positive impact of motor activity programs on social skills in ASD may be linked to multiple underlying mechanisms. These programs provide a structured setting where students can practice social skills in a safe and supportive environment, learning and applying social rules, interpreting social cues, and engaging in reciprocal communication [73]. Exercise also improves physical fitness and releases mood-boosting endorphins, which can increase social confidence and reduce anxiety, leading to better social interactions [61]. Research suggests that the program's design, including the involvement of typically developing peers and social games, significantly affects the benefits to social skills for students with ASD [72, 75]. A thoughtful and individualized approach to program design is therefore crucial to maximize the positive impact on social skills development.

5. Neurobiological Basis of Motor Impairments

5.1 Cerebellar structure and function in ASD

Research increasingly suggests that the cerebellum, a brain structure typically linked to motor control, plays a significant role in the neurobiology of ASD. Alterations in the cerebellar hemispheres and vermis may affect motor coordination, balance, and even social-emotional processing [76, 77]. Functional neuroimaging reveals abnormal activity and connectivity patterns within cerebrotocerebellar circuits, indicating disruptions in communication between the cerebellum and other brain regions involved in motor planning, language processing, and social cognition [78, 79]. These findings, supported by cellular and molecular studies, imply that cerebellar dysfunction may contribute to the diverse symptoms observed in ASD. Besides its role in motor control, the cerebellum is involved in adaptive prediction, a cognitive function that enables us to anticipate and respond flexibly to changing environmental demands [80]. Individuals with ASD often struggle with adaptive prediction, which may contribute to social anxiety, sensory sensitivities, and insistence on sameness [80]. The atypical structure and function of the cerebellum in ASD, particularly in regions like the right Crus I/II, involved in higher-order cognitive functions, could disrupt these predictive processes [81, 79]. This new understanding of the cerebellum's role in ASD provides insights into the disorder's complex neurobiology and paves the way for developing targeted interventions, such as cerebellar neuromodulation, to address specific challenges associated with ASD [82].

5.2 Prospective motor control strategies in ASD

Individuals with ASD often struggle with prospective motor control, which involves anticipating and planning movements in advance. This difficulty can significantly impact their motor skills and overall development [83]. Unlike typically developing individuals, who use predictions to guide movement through feedforward control, individuals with ASD tend to rely on reactive control, adjusting their actions based on sensory feedback after a movement has started [83]. This atypical motor control strategy can lead to delayed motor development, difficulty acquiring new motor skills, and unusual movement patterns, commonly observed in individuals with ASD [84, 85]. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that considers both motor learning strategies and effective motor interventions. Research suggests that individuals with ASD may benefit more from visual instructions, such as demonstrations or picture cues, when learning new motor skills, rather than verbal instructions [84]. This highlights the importance of tailored teaching approaches. Motor interventions that incorporate engaging activities, such as games, sports, and dance, can promote the development of prospective control strategies by encouraging anticipation and planning [86]. Early intervention is crucial, as addressing motor delays and prospective control challenges in early childhood offers the greatest potential for improvement [67]. By enhancing prospective motor control, interventions can improve motor skills and contribute to broader benefits in social communication, adaptive behavior, and overall quality of life for individuals with ASD.

5.3 Relationship between motor skills level and autism severity

Motor impairments in individuals with ASD are not a coincidental feature, but rather closely tied to the overall severity of the condition [20]. Research consistently shows that motor skills and autistic symptomatology are negatively correlated. Individuals with more pronounced motor difficulties, including both gross and fine motor skills, tend to face greater challenges with core ASD symptoms, such as social communication impairments, restricted repetitive behaviors, and limitations in adaptive functioning [87, 88]. This association is not only evident in diagnosed individuals but also in younger siblings of children with ASD, who often exhibit early motor delays that may indicate later challenges with ASD-related features [89]. Several potential explanations exist for this complex relationship. Studies suggest that damaging *de novo* mutations, especially those disrupting gene function, are associated with more severe motor impairments in individuals with ASD [90]. This highlights the role of genetic factors in influencing both motor abilities and ASD severity. The interconnected nature of brain development may also lead to shared neurobiological foundations for motor and social-communicative challenges. This explains why individuals with more pronounced motor impairments often experience greater difficulties with core ASD symptoms [30]. This growing understanding underscores the importance of early and comprehensive motor skill assessments in ASD. These assessments enable the development of tailored interventions that address both motor challenges and core ASD symptoms, maximizing developmental potential.

6. Future Directions and Implications

Despite growing recognition of motor impairments as a significant aspect of ASD, substantial challenges and gaps remain in current research. A major limitation is the tendency to treat motor deficits as a homogeneous category, overlooking the wide spectrum of specific difficulties experienced by individuals with ASD [20]. This lack of specificity hinders the development of targeted interventions and limits our understanding of how individual differences in motor skills relate to other ASD challenges. Furthermore, although some studies suggest that early motor delays may predict later ASD severity [29], reliable and clinically useful screening tools for early identification are lacking [30]. This highlights the need for longitudinal research to establish clearer developmental trajectories of motor skills in ASD and inform timely interventions. A complex area requiring further investigation is the interconnected nature of motor and social impairments in ASD. Research consistently shows a high prevalence of both impairments [21], but the underlying neurobiological mechanisms remain poorly understood. Further research should prioritize understanding the interplay between brain regions and networks involved in motor control and social cognition, which may reveal shared neural substrates or developmental pathways [33, 34]. This understanding is crucial for developing holistic interventions that effectively address both motor and social challenges. Research gaps exist in understanding the complexities of postural control in ASD. Atypical sensory processing, particularly in the visual and somatosensory domains, contributes to postural instability [43, 44]. However, further research is needed to understand how these sensory differences interact with other factors, such as attentional demands and social stimuli, to influence balance control [41, 45]. Moreover, while distinct postural sway patterns in ASD show promise as potential diagnostic markers [48, 49], their reliability and validity require further investigation before they can be confidently integrated into clinical practice. Bridging the gap between research and clinical practice remains a significant challenge. It is crucial to translate findings into easily implementable, individualized interventions tailored to each individual's specific motor needs with ASD [30]. This requires developing targeted interventions and robust evaluation methods that go beyond standardized assessments to include ecologically valid measures of functional performance and real-world activity participation [67, 68, 71]. By addressing these research gaps and promoting collaboration among researchers, clinicians, and families, we can pave the way for more effective interventions and significantly enhance the lives of individuals with ASD.

7. Conclusion

This review highlights the importance of recognizing and addressing motor impairments as integral aspects of ASD. Motor difficulties, although often overshadowed by social communication and behavioral challenges, are prevalent and

persistent, affecting individuals throughout their lives. Key findings reveal a complex relationship between motor abilities and ASD presentation. Deficits in fine and gross motor skills, sensory processing, and motor planning significantly impact an individual's ability to engage with their environment, acquire new skills, and fully participate in social and academic life. Addressing motor challenges goes beyond improving physical coordination. Research shows a strong link between motor skills and the severity of core ASD symptoms. Individuals with more pronounced motor impairments often experience greater difficulties with social communication, exhibit more repetitive behaviors, and face greater adaptive functioning limitations. This interconnectedness highlights the need for a paradigm shift in ASD research and intervention, adopting a holistic perspective that considers the interplay of motor abilities, sensory processing, social cognition, and overall development. Research should prioritize understanding the complex neurobiological mechanisms underlying motor impairments in ASD. This includes exploring atypical sensory integration, investigating disrupted neural connectivity patterns, and deepening our understanding of cerebellar dysfunction in relation to motor control and social-cognitive processes. It is also crucial to develop sensitive and specific screening tools for early detection of motor impairments during development. Moreover, personalized interventions must be carefully designed and evaluated to cater to each individual's unique needs. By prioritizing these areas of inquiry and promoting collaboration among researchers, clinicians, and families, we can enhance our understanding of motor impairments in ASD. This will enable us to develop more effective interventions, empowering individuals with ASD to live more independently, self-determined, and fulfilling lives.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: The author has read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Lord C, Brugha TS, Charman T, Cusack J, Dumas G, Frazier T, et al. Autism spectrum disorder. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2020;6(1).
- [2] Tomchek SD, Little LM, Dunn W. Sensory pattern contributions to developmental performance in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Am J Occup Ther*. 2015;69(5):6905185040p1.
- [3] Hodges H, Fealko C, Soares N. Autism spectrum disorder: definition, epidemiology, causes, and clinical evaluation. *Transl Pediatr*. 2020;9(S1):S55–65.
- [4] Roman-Urrestarazu A, Dumas G, Warriier V. Naming autism in the right context. *JAMA Pediatr*. 2022;176(7):633.
- [5] Smerbeck A. The Survey of Favorite Interests and Activities: Assessing and understanding restricted interests in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Autism*. 2019;23(1):247–.
- [6] Schulz SE, Stevenson RA. Sensory hypersensitivity predicts repetitive behaviours in autistic and typically-developing children. *Autism*. 2019;23(4):1028–41.
- [7] Crawley JN, Heyer W-D, LaSalle JM. Autism and cancer share risk genes, pathways, and drug targets. *Trends Genet*. 2016;32(3):139–46.
- [8] Napolitano A, Schiavi S, La Rosa P, Rossi-Espagnet MC, Petrillo S, Bottino F, et al. Sex differences in autism Spectrum Disorder: Diagnostic, neurobiological, and behavioral features. *Front Psychiatry*. 2022;13.
- [9] Mutluer T, Aslan Genç H, Özcan Morey A, Yapici Eser H, Ertinmaz B, Can M, et al. Population-based psychiatric comorbidity in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder: A meta-analysis. *Front Psychiatry*. 2022;13.

- [10] Yoon S, Choi J, Lee W, Do J. Genetic and epigenetic etiology underlying autism spectrum disorder. *J Clin Med*. 2020;9(4):966.
- [11] Hegarty JP II, Pegoraro LFL, Lazzeroni LC, Raman MM, Hallmayer JF, Monterrey JC, et al. Genetic and environmental influences on structural brain measures in twins with autism spectrum disorder. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2020;25(10):2556–66.
- [12] Dajani DR, Burrows CA, Odriozola P, Baez A, Nebel MB, Mostofsky SH, et al. Investigating functional brain network integrity using a traditional and novel diagnostic system for neurodevelopmental disorders. *bioRxiv*. 2018.
- [13] Yamada T, Watanabe T, Sasaki Y. Are sleep disturbances a cause or consequence of autism spectrum disorder? *Psychiatry Clin Neurosci*. 2023;77(7):377–85.
- [14] Mosconi MW, Sweeney JA. Sensorimotor dysfunctions as primary features of autism spectrum disorders. *Sci China Life Sci*. 2015;58(10):1016–23.
- [15] Hirata S, Nakai A, Okuzumi H, Kitajima Y, Hosobuchi T, Kokubun M. Motor skills and social impairments in children with autism spectrum disorders: A pilot study using the Japanese version of the Developmental Coordination Disorder Questionnaire (DCDQ-J). *SAGE Open*. 2015;5(3):215824401560251.
- [16] Sáenz AA, Villemonteix T, Van Schuerbeek P, Baijot S, Septier M, Defresne P, et al. Motor abnormalities in attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder and Autism Spectrum Disorder are associated with regional grey matter volumes. *Front Neurol*. 2021;12.
- [17] Memari AH, Ghanouni P, Shayestehfar M, Ghaheri B. Postural control impairments in individuals with autism spectrum disorder: A critical review of current literature. *Asian J Sports Med*. 2014;5(3).
- [18] Lotan M. Barking up the wrong tree—motor-sensory elements as prodrome in autism. *Biomedicines*. 2024;12(6):1235.
- [19] Hawks Z, Constantino JN, Weichselbaum C, Marrus N. Accelerating motor skill acquisition for bicycle riding in children with ASD: A pilot study. *J Autism Dev Disord*. 2020;50(1):342–8.
- [20] Wang LAL, Petrulla V, Zampella CJ, Waller R, Schultz RT. Gross motor impairment and its relation to social skills in autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review and two meta-analyses. *Psychol Bull*. 2022;148(3–4):273–300.
- [21] Zhou B, Xu Q, Li H, Zhang Y, Li D, Dong P, et al. Motor impairments in Chinese toddlers with autism spectrum disorder and its relationship with social communicative skills. *Front Psychiatry*. 2022;13.
- [22] Belaire A, Colomer C, Maravé-Vivas M, Chiva-Bartoll O. Analysis of the motor performance of children with ASD and its relationship with personal and contextual variables. *Int J Dev Disabil*. 2022;68(4):558–66.
- [23] May T, Mcginley J, Murphy A, Hinkley T, Papadopoulos N, Williams KJ, et al. A multidisciplinary perspective on motor impairment as an early behavioural marker in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Aust Psychol*. 2016;51(4):296–303.
- [24] Paquet A, Olliac B, Bouvard M-P, Golse B, Vaivre-Douret L. The semiology of motor disorders in autism spectrum disorders as highlighted from a standardized neuro-psychomotor assessment. *Front Psychol*. 2016;7.
- [25] Bo J, Lee C-M, Colbert A, Shen B. Do children with autism spectrum disorders have motor learning difficulties? *Res Autism Spectr Disord*. 2016;23:50–62.
- [26] Linke AC, Kinnear MK, Kohli JS, Fong CH, Lincoln AJ, Carper RA, et al. Impaired motor skills and atypical functional connectivity of the sensorimotor system in 40- to 65-year-old adults with autism spectrum disorders. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2020;85:104–12.
- [27] Fulceri F, Grossi E, Contaldo A, Narzisi A, Apicella F, Parrini I, et al. Motor skills as moderators of core symptoms in autism spectrum disorders: Preliminary data from an exploratory analysis with artificial neural networks. *Front Psychol*. 2019;9.
- [28] Mody M, Shui AM, Nowinski LA, Golas SB, Ferrone C, O'Rourke JA, et al. Communication deficits and the motor system: Exploring patterns of associations in autism spectrum disorder (ASD). *J Autism Dev Disord*. 2017;47(1):155–62.

- [29] Wu Y-T, Tsao C-H, Huang H-C, Yang T-A, Li Y-J. Relationship between motor skills and language abilities in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Phys Ther.* 2021;101(5).
- [30] Zampella CJ, Wang LAL, Haley M, Hutchinson AG, de Marchena A. Motor skill differences in autism spectrum disorder: A clinically focused review. *Curr Psychiatry Rep.* 2021;23(10).
- [31] Craig F, Lorenzo A, Lucarelli E, Russo L, Fanizza I, Trabacca A. Motor competency and social communication skills in preschool children with autism spectrum disorder. *Autism Res.* 2018;11(6):893–902.
- [32] Kaur M, M. Srinivasan S, N. Bhat A. Comparing motor performance, praxis, coordination, and interpersonal synchrony between children with and without Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). *Res Dev Disabil.* 2018;72:79–95.
- [33] Li L, He C, Jian T, Guo X, Xiao J, Li Y, et al. Attenuated link between the medial prefrontal cortex and the amygdala in children with autism spectrum disorder: Evidence from effective connectivity within the “social brain.” *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry.* 2021;111(110147):110147.
- [34] Nebel MB, Eloyan A, Nettles CA, Sweeney KL, Ament K, Ward RE, et al. Intrinsic visual-motor synchrony correlates with social deficits in autism. *Biol Psychiatry.* 2016;79(8):633–41.
- [35] Kilroy E, Harrison L, Butera C, Jayashankar A, Cermak S, Kaplan J, et al. Unique deficit in embodied simulation in autism: An fMRI study comparing autism and developmental coordination disorder. *Hum Brain Mapp.* 2021;42(5):1532–46.
- [36] Bhat AN. Motor impairment increases in children with autism spectrum disorder as a function of social communication, cognitive and functional impairment, repetitive behavior severity, and comorbid diagnoses: A SPARK study report. *Autism Res.* 2021;14(1):202–19.
- [37] Ceccarelli SB, Ferrante C, Gazzola E, Marzocchi GM, Nobile M, Molteni M, et al. Fundamental motor skills intervention for children with autism spectrum disorder: A 10-year narrative review. *Children (Basel).* 2020;7(11):250.
- [38] Ahmed S, Waseem H, Sadaf A, Ashiq R, Basit H, Rose S. Daily living tasks affected by sensory and motor problems in children with autism aged 5-12 years. *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing.*
- [39] Khoury E, Carment L, Lindberg P, Gaillard R, Krebs M-O, Amado I. Aspects sensorimoteurs et motricité manuelle dans les troubles du spectre autistique : une revue de la littérature. *Encephale.* 2020;46(2):135–45.
- [40] Unruh KE, Martin LE, Magnon G, Vaillancourt DE, Sweeney JA, Mosconi MW. Cortical and subcortical alterations associated with precision visuomotor behavior in individuals with autism spectrum disorder. *J Neurophysiol.* 2019;122(4):1330–41.
- [41] Lim YH, Lee HC, Falkmer T, Allison GT, Tan T, Lee WL, et al. Effect of visual information on postural control in adults with autism spectrum disorder. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2019;49(12):4731–9.
- [42] Coll S-M, Foster NEV, Meilleur A, Brambati SM, Hyde KL. Sensorimotor skills in autism spectrum disorder: A meta-analysis. *Res Autism Spectr Disord.* 2020;76(101570):101570.
- [43] Doumas M, McKenna R, Murphy B. Postural control deficits in autism spectrum disorder: The role of sensory integration. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2016;46(3):853–61.
- [44] Li Y, Mache MA, Todd TA. Complexity of center of pressure in postural control for children with autism spectrum disorders was partially compromised. *J Appl Biomech.* 2019;35(3):190–5.
- [45] Ghanouni P, Memari A-H, Gharibzadeh S, Eghlidi J, Moshayedi P. Effect of social stimuli on postural responses in individuals with autism spectrum disorder. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2017;47(5):1305–13.
- [46] Kyvelidou A, DeVeney S, Katsavelis D. Development of infant sitting postural control in three groups of infants at various risk levels for autism spectrum disorder. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2023;20(2):1234.
- [47] Lim YH, Partridge K, Girdler S, Morris SL. Standing postural control in individuals with autism spectrum disorder: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2017;47(7):2238–53.

- [48] Lidstone DE, Miah FZ, Poston B, Beasley JF, Dufek JS. Examining the specificity of postural control deficits in children with Autism Spectrum Disorder using a cross-syndrome approach. *Res Autism Spectr Disord.* 2020;72(101514):101514.
- [49] Miller HL, Caçola PM, Sherrod GM, Patterson RM, Bugnariu NL. Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder, Developmental Coordination Disorder, and typical development differ in characteristics of dynamic postural control: A preliminary study. *Gait Posture.* 2019;67:9–11.
- [50] Tsiros MD, Shahrin S, Mackintosh S, Thewlis D. Setting up girls for success in fundamental motor skills: The role of balance in 8-10 year olds. *J Sports Sci.* 2022;40(19):2200–7.
- [51] Mache MA, Todd TA. Gross motor skills are related to postural stability and age in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Res Autism Spectr Disord.* 2016;23:179–87.
- [52] Simpson A, Al Ruwaili R, Jolley R, Leonard H, Geeraert N, Riggs KJ. Fine motor control underlies the association between response inhibition and drawing skill in early development. *Child Dev.* 2019;90(3):911–23.
- [53] Adolph KE, Hoch JE. The importance of motor skills for development. In: Nestlé Nutrition Institute Workshop Series. S. Karger AG; 2020. p. 136–44.
- [54] Saruco E, Di Rienzo F, Nunez-Nagy S, Rubio-Gonzalez MA, Jackson PL, Collet C, et al. Anodal tDCS over the primary motor cortex improves motor imagery benefits on postural control: A pilot study. *Sci Rep.* 2017;7(1).
- [55] Gandolfi M, Fiorio M, Geroïn C, Prior M, De Marchi S, Amboni M, et al. Motor dual task with eyes closed improves postural control in patients with functional motor disorders: A posturographic study. *Gait Posture.* 2021;88:286–91.
- [56] Lin L-Y, Chi I-J, Sung Y-S. Mediating effect of sequential memory on the relationship between visual-motor integration and self-care performance in young children with autism spectrum disorder. *Front Psychol.* 2022;13.
- [57] Desaunay P, Briant AR, Bowler DM, Ring M, Gérardin P, Baleyte J-M, et al. Memory in autism spectrum disorder: A meta-analysis of experimental studies. *Psychol Bull.* 2020;146(5):377–410.
- [58] Landsiedel J, Williams DM. Increasing extrinsic motivation improves time-based prospective memory in adults with autism: Relations with executive functioning and mentalizing. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2020;50(4):1133–46.
- [59] Justus SA, Powell PS, Duarte A. Intact context memory performance in adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11(1).
- [60] Wang L, Xie T, Ma H, Xu M, Xie X. Subject-performed task effect on working memory performance in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Autism Res.* 2022;15(9):1698–709.
- [61] Yu CCW, Wong SWL, Lo FSF, So RCH, Chan DFY. Study protocol: a randomized controlled trial study on the effect of a game-based exercise training program on promoting physical fitness and mental health in children with autism spectrum disorder. *BMC Psychiatry.* 2018;18(1).
- [62] Tan BWZ, Pooley JA, Speelman CP. A meta-analytic review of the efficacy of physical exercise interventions on cognition in individuals with autism spectrum disorder and ADHD. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2016;46(9):3126–43.
- [63] Teh EJ, Vijayakumar R, Tan TXJ, Yap MJ. Effects of physical exercise interventions on stereotyped motor behaviours in children with ASD: A meta-analysis. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2022;52(7):2934–57.
- [64] Toscano CVA, Ferreira JP, Quinaud RT, Silva KMN, Carvalho HM, Gaspar JM. Exercise improves the social and behavioral skills of children and adolescent with autism spectrum disorders. *Front Psychiatry.* 2022;13.
- [65] Hu X, Ou Y, Li J, Sun M, Ge Q, Pan Y, et al. Voluntary exercise to reduce anxiety behaviour in traumatic brain injury shown to alleviate inflammatory brain response in mice. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023;24(7):6365.
- [66] Firth J, Rosenbaum S, Stubbs B, Gorchynski P, Yung AR, Vancampfort D. Motivating factors and barriers towards exercise in severe mental illness: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychol Med.* 2016;46(14):2869–81.
- [67] Ketcheson L, Hauck J, Ulrich D. The effects of an early motor skill intervention on motor skills, levels of physical activity, and socialization in young children with autism spectrum disorder: A pilot study. *Autism.* 2017;21(4):481–92.

- [68] Amonkar N, Delepine E, Takillapati S, Myers C, Patel B, Cleffi C, et al. Effects of a whole-body general movement intervention on motor performance, agility, and locomotor skills of children with autism spectrum disorder: Results from a comparison between face-to-face and telehealth-based intervention delivery. *Iproceedings*. 2022;8(1):e39337.
- [69] Kaur M, Bhat A. Creative yoga intervention improves motor and imitation skills of children with autism spectrum disorder. *Phys Ther*. 2019;99(11):1520–34.
- [70] Kaplánová A, Šišková N, Grznárová T, Vanderka M. Physical education and development of locomotion and gross motor skills of children with autism spectrum disorder. *Sustainability*. 2022;15(1):28.
- [71] Jin Y-R, Sung Y-S, Koh C-L, Chu SY, Yang H-C, Lin L-Y. Efficacy of motor interventions on functional performance among preschool children with autism spectrum disorder: A pilot randomized controlled trial. *Am J Occup Ther*. 2023;77(6).
- [72] Sansi A, Nalbant S, Ozer D. Effects of an inclusive physical activity program on the motor skills, social skills and attitudes of students with and without autism spectrum disorder. *J Autism Dev Disord*. 2021;51(7):2254–70.
- [73] Zhao M, Chen S. The effects of structured physical activity program on social interaction and communication for children with autism. *Biomed Res Int*. 2018;2018:1–13.
- [74] Colombo-Dougovito AM, Block ME. Fundamental motor skill interventions for children and adolescents on the autism spectrum: A literature review. *Rev J Autism Dev Disord*. 2019;6(2):159–71.
- [75] Sefen JAN, Al-Salmi S, Shaikh Z, AlMulhem JT, Rajab E, Fredericks S. Beneficial use and potential effectiveness of physical activity in managing autism spectrum disorder. *Front Behav Neurosci*. 2020;14.
- [76] Zhao G, Walsh K, Long J, Gui W, Denisova K. Reduced structural complexity of the right cerebellar cortex in male children with autism spectrum disorder. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(7):e0196964.
- [77] Hanaie R, Mohri I, Kagitani-Shimono K, Tachibana M, Matsuzaki J, Hirata I, et al. Aberrant cerebellar–cerebral functional connectivity in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Front Hum Neurosci*. 2018;12.
- [78] Crippa A, Del Vecchio G, Busti Ceccarelli S, Nobile M, Arrigoni F, Brambilla P. Cortico-cerebellar connectivity in autism spectrum disorder: What do we know so far? *Front Psychiatry*. 2016;7.
- [79] Stoodley CJ, D’Mello AM, Ellegood J, Jakkamsetti V, Liu P, Nebel MB, et al. Altered cerebellar connectivity in autism and cerebellar-mediated rescue of autism-related behaviors in mice. *Nat Neurosci*. 2017;20(12):1744–51.
- [80] Frosch IR, Mittal VA, D’Mello AM. Cerebellar contributions to social cognition in ASD: A predictive processing framework. *Front Integr Neurosci*. 2022;16.
- [81] D’Mello AM, Stoodley CJ. Cerebro-cerebellar circuits in autism spectrum disorder. *Front Neurosci*. 2015;9.
- [82] Clausi S, Olivito G, Siciliano L, Lupo M, Laghi F, Baiocco R, et al. The cerebellum is linked to theory of mind alterations in autism. A direct clinical and MRI comparison between individuals with autism and cerebellar neurodegenerative pathologies. *Autism Res*. 2021;14(11):2300–13.
- [83] Ekberg TL, Falck-Ytter T, Bölte S, Gredebäck G, Ekberg TL, Gredebäck G, et al. Reduced prospective motor control in 10-month-Olds at risk for autism spectrum disorder. *Clin Psychol Sci*. 2016;4(1):129–35.
- [84] Ruggeri A, Dancel A, Johnson R, Sargent B. The effect of motor and physical activity intervention on motor outcomes of children with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review. *Autism*. 2020;24(3):544–68.
- [85] Bremer E, Balogh R, Lloyd M. Effectiveness of a fundamental motor skill intervention for 4-year-old children with autism spectrum disorder: A pilot study. *Autism*. 2015;19(8):980–91.
- [86] Lourenço C, Esteves D. Motor intervention and assessment instruments in autism spectrum disorders. *Creat Educ*. 2019;10(08):1929–36.
- [87] Cvijetic M, Gagic S. Relationship between motor abilities and severity of autism spectrum disorder. *Spec Edukac Rehabil*. 2017;16(1):35–54.

[88] Bhat AN, Boulton AJ, Tulsy DS. A further study of relations between motor impairment and social communication, cognitive, language, functional impairments, and repetitive behavior severity in children with ASD using the SPARK study dataset. *Autism Res.* 2022;15(6):1156–78.

[89] Garrido D, Petrova D, Watson LR, Garcia-Retamero R, Carballo G. Language and motor skills in siblings of children with autism spectrum disorder: A meta-analytic review. *Autism Res.* 2017;10(11):1737–50.

[90] Buja A, Volfovsky N, Krieger AM, Lord C, Lash AE, Wigler M, et al. Damaging de novo mutations diminish motor skills in children on the autism spectrum. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2018;115(8).

Bryan V. Catama, Dev Ed.D

College Supervisor

Saint Louis University

School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts

Baguio City, Philippines

E-mail: bvcatama@slu.edu.ph